

1 Excellence #@REL-EVA-RE@#**1.1 Quality and pertinence of the project's research and innovation objectives (and the extent to which they are ambitious, and go beyond the state of the art)** #@QUA-LIT-QL@#

Introduction and State of the art: The European Union plans to expand its installed offshore wind capacity from 25 Gigawatts (GW) in 2021 to 60 GW¹ in 2030 to achieve the target of sourcing 32% of its energy from renewable sources². This objective is key to alleviate climate change and ensure EU energetic independence in an unstable geopolitical context. The EU is one of the world-leaders in offshore wind development and this field was signposted as a priority for research and innovation³.

The increasing demand of installed power requires the unlocking of deeper water locations for development, where innovative wind platforms are necessary. Offshore wind developments have been dominated by fixed-bottom foundations, which are limited to water depth (50m – 70m) by economical and technical restrictions⁴. The development at deep water areas (>60 m) is ineluctable, as they allow access to strong and stable wind conditions⁵. Europe is at the forefront of floating wind innovation with pilot projects built in Scotland (Hywind), Portugal (Windfloat-Atlantic), France (Floatgen and NextFloat) and Norway (Hywind Tampen). The following stage is the installation of large-scale commercial wind farms using up to 100 wind turbines.

Cost reduction and capabilities of the chain supply are the two main challenges for the offshore wind industry. On one hand, reducing the cost of mooring systems, which can account for 10% to 15% of a wind farm investment, then is crucial to ensure their economic viability. On the other hand, the supply chain (factories, ports, vessels) is not ready to cope with the hundreds of anchors that would be necessary to manufacture and install in a large-scale wind farm. Therefore, **the optimization of anchor design is essential to achieve the 60GW target of installed offshore wind energy capacity.**

Anchor sharing is a means of reducing the number of anchors to be installed, implying less installation time, less consumption of steel (reduced carbon footprint) and a reduced pressure on the supply chain. Shared anchors could reduce the mooring system costs and the number of anchors to be manufactured at an order of 16% considering a windfarm with 100 turbines⁶. In a shared anchor, several mooring lines (Figure 1), are connected to a single anchor⁷. Several types of anchors have been utilized in the offshore industry at deep-water locations: piles, suction caissons, drag anchors and penetrating anchors (Figure 1), known as embedded anchors⁸. Due to symmetry and mobilization of the strength of the surrounding soil, piles and suction caissons are suitable alternatives for shared anchors.

While the first example of a floating wind farm with shared anchors at Hywind Tampen, few researches and no guidance address the design of shared anchors formulating unknowns for large scale developments. Current guidance has been developed for the oil and gas industry, where anchors are associated to a single mooring line (unidirectional loading). Three or six mooring lines are expected to be attached to a single anchor, all applying a combination of vertical (tensile) and horizontal cyclic loads, not necessarily in phase creating a complex soil structure interaction problem (multidirectional loading). The existing research and design methodologies that have been developed for mooring anchors come from the offshore oil and gas industry, where floating facilities are connected to single anchors (unidirectional loading). This condition has been broadly studied experimentally^{9 10} and numerically^{11 12}. Moving to

Figure 1. Schematic of shared anchors for floating wind turbines.

¹ European Commission, (2020), "An EU strategy to harness the potential of offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral future", Communication COM(2020)/741.

² European Commission. "Renewable energy targets". <https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/renewable-energy-directive-targets-and-rules/renewable-energy-targets_en>

³ European Commission (2019), Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Joint Research Centre, "The strategic energy technology (SET) plan", Publications Office.

⁴ Jiang, Z., (2021), Installation of offshore wind turbines: A technical review. Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. Vol 139, April 2021

⁵ Wind Europe (2021), Offshore Wind in Europe. Key trends and statistics 2020.

⁶ Fontana, C (2019) "A Multiline Anchor Concept for Floating Offshore Wind Turbines" PhD Thesis, University of Massachusetts Amherst.

⁷ Adapted from: Zhao, L., et al., 2020, Centrifuge observations on multidirectional loading of a suction caisson in dense sand. Acta Geotechnica. Vol 15, pp-1439-1451.

⁸ Randolph, M., Gourvenec, S., 2011, "Offshore geotechnical engineering" Routledge.

⁹ Wang, X., Yang, X., Zeng, X., 2017, Centrifuge modeling of lateral bearing behavior of offshore wind turbine with suction bucket foundation in sand. Ocean Engineering.

¹⁰ Jeong, Y.H., Bae, J.S., Kim, J.H. et al., 2022, "Cyclic Behavior of Bucket Anchor Foundation in Silty Sand under Sustained Pull-Out Loads via Centrifuge Model Tests". KSCE J Civ Eng 26, 1632–1642.

¹¹ A. S. Kiran, R. Vijaya and S. V. Sivapriya., 2015, "Estimation of pull out capacity of suction anchors in soft clays using numerical modelling," 2015 IEEE Underwater Technology (UT), pp. 1-4.

¹² Choo, Yun Wook, Kim, Surin, Choi, Hoyoung, Kim, Jae-Hyun, Kim, Dong-Soo, and Dong-Joon Kim., 2012, "Behavior of Suction Anchor For Horizontal Load From Catenary Line In Cohesionless Soils." Paper presented at the The Twenty-second International Offshore and Polar Engineering Conference, Rhodes, Greece.

a bi-directional cyclic load condition, the response of shared anchors suggest that: in sands, two-way cyclic loading results in densification of the surrounding soil increasing the lateral resistance and reducing the deflections of the soil/anchor system¹³; in clays, bi-directional cyclic load below a critical threshold can contribute to the soil/anchor lateral loading capacity, however in this case there is an accumulation of permanent displacements that may compromise the long-term serviceability of the anchor¹⁴.

In the framework of renewable energies, the situation of multidirectional (> two directions) load on on shared anchors has been recently addressed for anchors embedded in sand at the University of Western Australia¹² and at the University of Southampton¹⁵ (SEAMLESS project). However, no research has been reported regarding the the multidirectional (> two dimensions) loading capacity of shared anchors installed in clay. In Europe, geotechnical investigation reports for offshore wind farms in the Irish Sea and the North Sea indicate the presence of clays within the seabed¹⁶. In Asia and North America is common the presence of soft marine clays at the seabed at water depths in the range of influence of floating wind farms^{17 18}. Hywind Scotland is an example of a floating wind farm with anchors installed in very soft to firm clay. Therefore, as the offshore wind industry moves to new locations in which clay deposits can be found, further work is required to better understand anchors performance under multidirectional cyclic loads including conditions large enough to induce anchor failure, loads representative of sea states and numerical modelling of multi-line loading to better characterize the physics of their response to loading.

The presence of clay deposits at various worldwide seabed locations and the potential of floating wind farms to harvest wind resources located in deep water sites motivates ShareWind to **provide design guidelines and evaluate the loading capacity of shared anchors -piles and suction anchors- installed in clayey seabed to sustain the loads of multiple wind turbines**. Shared anchors can contribute in making floating wind energy more cost-competitive and it is important to understand the new system dynamics that arise.

Objectives: ShareWind aims to **provide design recommendations on shared anchors installed in clay as a feasible alternative to reduce costs of Offshore Floating Wind Farms**. ShareWind will employ physical and numerical modelling to establish the threshold level of multidirectional loading under which there is a safe or stable response of shared anchors installed in clay. The specific objectives of ShareWind have assigned a specific Work Package (WP) and key performance indicators (KPI) to measure their fulfillment.

-O1)WP1: to determine load conditions, geometry of the anchors and seabed characteristics involved in sharing anchors as a system to sustain the dynamic loads from floating wind turbines. This stage will delimit representative real conditions of offshore environments as an input for the physical and numerical models to be developed in **WP2** and **WP3**. **KPI1:** secondment completed at a specialized institution to enhance skills in this topic and consolidate research collaborations outside the host institution.

- O2)WP2: to physically model multidirectional loading of anchors embedded in clay. Reduced scale models of real anchors will be tested in the enhanced gravitational level of the Uni. Eiffel geotechnical centrifuge. **KPI2:** Number of centrifuge experiments performed and number of anchors tested according to the project schedule.

- O3) WP3: to numerically model the behaviour of shared anchors. Here, models as Soft-Soil¹⁹, Hypoplasticity²⁰ and Saniclay²¹ will be implemented in numerical simulations by finite element method. It will be also implemented the Digital Twins concept by performing preliminary numerical simulations of the models to be tested in the centrifuge. The Digital Twins evolve as the project takes place moving from initial predictions of the experimental response to refined virtual replicas based on the data collected from the sensors during the centrifuge tests. **KPI3:** number of numerical and constitutive models employed to simulate the experimental response.

- O4)WP4: to examine different geometry characteristics of shared anchors and soil conditions (very soft clay, soft clay and lightly over consolidated clay, more than three mooring lines connected, different anchor diameters and lengths) to provide design guidelines and failure envelopes. **KPI4:** secondment completed at a specialized institution to enhance skills in this topic and consolidate additional research collaborations outside the host institution.

- O5)WP5: to disseminate, communicate and exploit the project outcomes to maximize their impact in the academic, industry and non-academic community (developed in section 2.2). **KPI5:** the number of deliverables submitted as proposed in the dissemination plan of the project in accordance to the schedule of the project.

¹³ Herduin, M. Multi-Directional loading on shared anchors for offshore renewable energy. PhD thesis Univ. of Western Australia.

¹⁴ Burns, M., et al., 2014. Centrifuge modelling of suction caissons under orthogonal double line loading International Conference on Physical Modelling in Geotechnics -ICPMG2014, pp 465–471

¹⁵ SharEd Anchor Multidirectional Load Envelopes with Strength Synthesis (SEAMLESS). <<https://supergen-ore.net/projects/seamless>>

¹⁶ Ahayan, S., 2019, "A constitutive Model for natural Clays: From Laboratory testing to Modelling of Offshore Monopiles". PhD thesis, Ecole Centrale de Nantes – Université de Liège.

¹⁷ Zhixian W, Chuanwen J, Qian A, Chengmin W.,2009, "The key technology of offshore wind farm and its new development in China". Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. 2009;13(1):216-22

¹⁸ Malhotra, S. "Design and Construction Considerations for Offshore Wind Turbine Foundations." Proc. of the ASME 2007 26th International Conference on Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering. San Diego, California, USA. June 10–15, 2007. pp. 635-647. ASME.

¹⁹ Vermeer PA, Neher HP ,1999, "A soft soil model that accounts for creep". In: Beyond 2000 in Computational Geotechnics, Brinkgreve RBJ (ed.). Rotterdam: Balkema, 249-261.

²⁰ Masin, D., 2014, "Clay hypoplasticity model including stiffness anisotropy", Géotechnique, 64(3) pp.232-238.

²¹ Dafalias, Y.F., Manzari, M.T., Papadimitriou, A.G., 2006, "SANICLAY: simple anisotropic clay plasticity model", International Journal for Numerical Methods in Geomechanics, 30(12), pp. 1231-1257.

- **O6) WP6: to enhance career perspectives, employability and acquire new scientific and transferable skills** by developing a career development plan (developed in section 2.1). **KPI6:** the number of training activities taken by the Experienced Researcher in accordance to a structured career development plan.

Project innovation: the outcomes of ShareWind will allow to optimize the implementation of shared anchors in regions with predominantly clayey soils at the seabed. In addition, no real numerical simulations on shared anchors in clay has been published. ShareWind involves the development of an innovative experimental setup implementing technologies as 3D photogrammetry and the application of the Digital Twins framework to create digital assets of the experiments. The results of ShareWind will be integrated in unified design frameworks to predict the loading capacity and displacements of shared anchors covering the soil types found in offshore environments (from sand to clay). Such integration of knowledge will ultimately lead to improved design of anchor systems with direct impacts in their long-term performance and in the optimization of costs of floating wind farms in Europe and worldwide.

1.2 Soundness of the proposed methodology (including interdisciplinary approaches, consideration of the gender dimension and other diversity aspects if relevant for the research project, and the quality of open science practices)

The project is divided in 6 aims, addressed by 4 scientific and 2 transversal Work Packages (see section 3.1).

Methodology: in **WP1** the load conditions, number of loading cycles, geometry of the anchors and seabed shear strength parameters will be defined as a basis of the information required to develop the physical experiments and numerical models of **WP2** and **WP3**. This information will be retrieved during the first secondment period (3 months) at the Norwegian Geotechnical Institute (NGI), using data from previous developments of anchors for floating wind turbines developed by the Institute (e.g., Hywind Scotland)²², databases of laboratory testing and information from sites identified by the NGI suitable for floating offshore wind solutions.

WP2 is divided into three subtasks: **WP2.1** devoted to development of a detailed experimental setup to simulate the application of multidirectional load in anchors installed in soft clay (suction anchors and piles), **WP2.2** to perform centrifuge tests and **WP2.3** to determine experimental failure envelopes of the anchors to evaluate their loading capacity. In **WP2.1** it will be employed centrifuge modelling, an experimental method that reproduces the strength and stiffness of the soil for small-scale models²³. It requires large facilities and special equipment, available in few research institutes in the world as the geotechnical centrifuge at the Uni. Eiffel in Nantes. To reproduce the seabed strength conditions defined in **WP1**, reconstituted normally consolidated clay, will be prepared using kaolin clay, a material widely used in centrifuge testing for offshore geotechnical engineering problems²⁴. The outcomes of **WP2.1** are the detailed geometry of the experimental setup defining the location of the sensors to monitor the displacements and forces applied to the anchors and a checklist of steps to perform the centrifuge experiments to ensure its repeatability.

In **WP2.2**, the piles and suction anchors will be realistically installed in the clay following methodologies developed at the Uni.Eiffel^{25 26}. Two types of connections between the anchor and mooring lines will be studied, catenary and semi-taut as they are commonly used in offshore anchors. In the case of the catenary line, the load applied will arrive horizontally to the anchor. In a semi-taut line, the load will arrive with an inclined component (δ) at angles ranging between 30° and 40° . Figure 2²⁷ presents a schematic of the setup proposed to simulate the load conditions in a shared anchor. It consists of a system of three actuators placed at the top of a container which defines the boundaries of the model. The actuators are vertically coupled to mooring lines (cables), then a set of pulleys shift the direction of the cables to connect them to the anchor. To monitor the response of the models, displacement transducers will be installed in the anchors and force cells will monitor and control the forces applied by the actuators. In a centrifuge experiment it is possible to test from three to four anchors. **A total of five centrifuge tests are defined for ShareWind, meaning a total of 15 to 20 anchors tested.** **WP2.2** will characterize the soil strength and identify the soil failure mechanism of the soil/anchor system. The soil strength characterization will be carried out by means Cone Penetration Tests during the centrifuge experiments. The failure mechanism identification will use

²² NGI Project Hywind Anchor foundation. <https://www.ngi.no/eng/Projects/Hywind-anchor-foundation>

²³ Schofield, A.N. (1980). Cambridge Geotechnical Centrifuge Operations. Géotechnique, 30(3): 227-268.

²⁴ Springman SM (1993) Centrifuge modelling in clay: marine applications. Technical Report CUED/D-SOILS/TR260. University of Cambridge. Department of engineering.

²⁵ Thorel, L., Garnier, J., Rault, G., Dendani, H., Colliat, J., 2010, "Installation process of suction anchors in Gulf of Guinea clay : Centrifuge

modelling". 7th international Conference on Physical Modelling in Geotechnics.

²⁶ Khemakhen, M., Chenaf, N., Garnier, J., Rault, G., Thorel, L., 2010 "Static and cyclic lateral pile behavior in clay". 7th international Conference on Physical Modelling in Geotechnics

²⁷ Photo source of Prototype anchor <<https://www.sptoffshore.com/pipelay-startup-anchors/>>

photogrammetry and 3D scanning to produce virtual reconstructions of the models tested in the centrifuge before and after the application of the monotonic and cyclic loads. Those virtual copies will allow the inspection of the region around the anchors to observe and measure the induced deformations in the soil/anchor system. This can be achieved using affordable (less than 500€) 3D scanners or Lidar sensors and the reconstruction of the virtual model can be done using tools such as Blender (open source)²⁸ implemented in the animation industry.

In **WP2.3** the experimental loading capacity and anchor performance will be addressed. **WP2.3** will develop experimental failure envelopes, defined as the combination of horizontal (Fx) and vertical (Fy) loads that cause the failure of the soil. Figure 3 presents the construction of a failure envelope from the application of a monotonic load in one direction as a benchmark condition (Fig.3a). In a second stage, the failure envelope evaluates the preloading effect in one direction and loading in a different direction and how this sequence falls in the space inside the failure envelope (Fig. 3b). In a third stage the failure envelope summarizes the condition of the application of cyclic multidirectional load is applied (Fig. 3c). From the failure envelope stability contours will be defined to determine regions in which the soil/anchor system falls into an unstable (rupture of the soil affecting the overall anchor stability), meta-stable or stable condition when subjected to a cyclic loading sequence (Fig. 3d).

Figure 3. Multidirectional and cyclic loading inside a failure envelope and stability contour diagram

In **WP3.1** initial numerical simulations will be carried out with preliminary geometry and soil conditions defined in **WP1.1**. The aim is to produce the first Digital Twins of the experiments and retrieve initial failure envelopes before the centrifuge experiments. A second subtask (**WP3.2**) integrates the Digital Twins with the centrifuge experiments through the installed sensors in the models and the exchange of data to further refine the virtual models. In **WP3.2** it will be evaluated the hypothesis that not all the selected models are able to capture the clay behavior under multidirectional loading Figure 4 shows the integration of the physical models with their virtual versions constituting Digital Twins and the outcomes of this implementation in the creation of virtual assets with immersive visualization, the development of predictive models and a decision-making tool.

Figure 4. Physical model and Digital Twins integration

WP4 will move to parametric simulations under various anchor geometry (diameter, length), soil type (soft, stiff clay) and load conditions. The Digital Twins will use finite element modelling to predict the soil/anchor stresses and deformations during the application of the loads. For this project, the numerical simulations can be carried out in Plaxis 3D²⁹ as it is widely used in the offshore geotechnical industry and the Experienced Researcher (ER) has previous experience and training on its utilization. One of the challenges in **WP3** and **WP4** is the selection of the constitutive models (Soft-Soil, Hypoplasticity and SANICLAY) to reproduce the clay cyclic soil behavior: degradation of strength and stiffness as well as shear strain accumulation. At the end of **WP4** design charts and equations will be delivered to predict the loading capacity and soil deformation of the anchors subjected to various cases of multidirectional cyclic load (1, 2, 3 directions) to identify critical design conditions and to determine how the failure envelope changes in shape and size during the application of the monotonic and cyclic loads. For the development of the parametric studies of **WP4** the ER will participate in a secondment period at the University of Southampton (3 months) to post-process the numerical analyses and work in the evaluation of the constitutive models and the integration of experimental and numerical failure envelopes of the soil/anchor systems.

Integration of methods and disciplines to pursue the objectives: ShareWind will integrate the expertise and methods from several disciplines and researchers including the ER. In **WP1**, during the secondment at the NGI, the ER will work with Dr. T. Langford, NGI director of offshore energy³⁰ to expand the ER knowledge in the in the geotechnical design of anchor systems (*civil-structural engineering*) and the characterization of sites suitable for floating wind solutions (*geology-geotechnical engineering*). In **WP2** the ER will implement the centrifuge modeling techniques developed at the Uni.Eiffel, including the installation of anchors, the preparation of reconstituted soils

²⁸ Blender. <https://www.blender.org/>

²⁹ Plaxis 3D Geotechnical Analysis Software. <https://www.bentley.com/en/products/product-line/geotechnical-engineering-software/plaxis-3d>

³⁰ NGI – Offshore Energy < <https://www.ngi.no/eng/Market-areas/Offshore-Energy>>

and strength characterization of soils at the enhanced gravitational field of the centrifuge experiments (*mechanical and geotechnical engineering*). **WP2** the ER will implement in ShareWind *photogrammetry* and *3D graphics* techniques to develop Digital Twins of the centrifuge experiments as a methodology to identify foundation failure mechanisms. In **WP3** and **WP4**, during the secondment period at Southampton the ER will be mentored by Dr. B. Cerfontaine³¹ (MSCA fellow in 2020) and Prof. S. Gourvenec³⁶, bringing to ShareWind and the host laboratory numerical modelling approaches to simulate complex loading on offshore anchors and the concept of whole life geotechnical design in which the soil-structure response varies with time as the soil geotechnical properties evolve, a pioneer approach with potential impact in the future design of offshore renewable energy infrastructure³².

Gender dimension and other diversity aspects: in the context of this research project, gender dimension and other diversity aspects are not relevant. The research activities do not involve human beings as subjects of research.

Open science practices: following the Horizon Europe Programme Guide (2022), Sharewind will implement: **i) Early and open sharing of research**, by preregistration of the research plan in the project repository accompanying a standardized template (i.e., AsPredicted³³). Preprint records of scientific manuscripts to be submitted in research journals available in the project data repository; **ii) Research Data Management** by ensuring that the data of the project can be freely accessible, reused and published by anyone without restrictions of copyright (Open Data) following the FAIR principles; **iii) Measures to ensure reproducibility of results** ShareWind will have experimental and numerical modelling components. At the end of each centrifuge test, standardized data papers will be prepared following Uni.Eiffel template. In the context of the numerical simulations, data reports will present the workflows to reproduce the simulations (steps to build the numerical model geometries, boundary conditions, definition of materials and application of loads), the employed software and its version so that all results should be reproducible; **iv) Open access to research outputs** by ensuring that the resulting scientific publications will be available as open access via green or golden route. Open Access will be provided to conference proceedings, reports, data sets and grey literature.

Research data management and management of other research outputs: in line with the FAIR data principles, ShareWind will follow the guidelines of the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template³⁴. The data repository for this project will be Uni.Eiffel Dataverse³⁵, to deposit research papers, data sets, reports and all the digital artefacts developed. The Data Management Plan (**a deliverable of WP5**) for ShareWind will consider the following points: **i) Data Summary**, describing the type of data, properties and file formats, estimated data size, software employed to register and read the data specific characteristics of the data; **ii) FAIR data:** Findable (F), the produced data will have assigned unique persistent identifiers (DOI), to guarantee the discoverability of the data, metadata will be allocated following the Uni. Eiffel repository standards (Dublin Core). Accessible (A), the research outcomes and metadata of ShareWind will be available and downloadable with no access restrictions from the project repository. Interoperable (I), employing open non-proprietary formats to store and share the research results. Reusable (R), indicating the license details in the metafiles. Each project folder in the repository will include README files to ensure interpretation and reanalysis of the data by others. To further increase visibility of the research articles and preprints, copies will be deposited in the French Open Archive HAL.

1.3 Quality of the supervision, training and of the two-way transfer of knowledge between the researcher and the host.

Qualifications and experience of the supervisor(s): Dr Luc Thorel³⁶ has excellent expertise, resources, and collaborations for this research project and is experienced in training post-docs and guiding them to independent scientific careers. He is currently senior research and deputy head of the department of geotechnics, environment, natural risks and earth sciences (GERS) of the Uni.Eiffel³⁷, campus Nantes. Dr Thorel is a world expert in physical modelling in geotechnics, particularly with geotechnical centrifuge with a broad record of publications covering topics as: soil-structure interaction under complex loading, deep, shallow foundations and offshore geotechnics: 68 papers in peer reviewed journals, 174 communications in conferences, 78 research reports for industry. Therefore, working at his laboratory is an opportunity for the ER to become part of his team and have access to this expertise. Recent applications of his research have been oriented towards anchoring systems for renewable marine energy projects (REDENV-EOL³⁸). He co-supervised 15 Ph.D students, 5 postdoctoral researchers, currently working as researchers and lecturers in prestigious universities and senior engineers in multinational companies. He also was member of 44 PhD jury, including 19 times as a rapporteur. Therefore, he has an excellent track record in guiding and mentoring young researchers. He has been and is currently working in Regional, National, European and

³¹ Dr. B. Cerfontaine – Prof. Susan Gourvenec. <<https://www.southampton.ac.uk/people/5y6tqr/doctor-benjamin-cerfontaine>> <<https://www.southampton.ac.uk/people/5xlfgx/professor-susan-gourvenec>>

³² Gourvenec, S, 2022, “ Whole Life Design: Theory and Applications of This New Approach to Offshore Geotechnics”. Indian. Geot. Journal.

³³ ASPREDICTED (domain-general registry service providing standardised preregistration template) <<https://aspredicted.org/>>

³⁴ Horizon Europe «Data Management Plan Template (HE) » V1.0 5/5/2021

³⁵ Université Gustave Eiffel Dataverse < [data.univ-gustave-eiffel](https://data.univ-gustave-eiffel.fr/) >

³⁶ Dr. Luc Thorel personal website <<https://pagespro.univ-gustave-eiffel.fr/luc-thorel> >

³⁷ GERS – Université Gustave Eiffel. <https://gers.univ-gustave-eiffel.fr/>

³⁸ <https://www.weamec.fr/en/projects/redenv-eol>

International Research programs and collaborations, as well as in Industry research activities: coordinator of ANR-ASIRI+³⁹, Uni.Eiffel representant in GEOLAB⁴⁰, and coordinator of West Atlantic Marine Community projects as REDENV-EOL. In the framework of ShareWind, Dr Thorel: i) will facilitate the access to the research equipment, resources and facilities at the Uni.Eiffel; ii) will support the ER career development plan by facilitating networking opportunities (technical visits to offshore wind farms, training) in France, where research and development in floating offshore wind is in progress (Floatgen⁸, Eolink⁴¹, NextFloat⁹). Then, the ER will have access to key scientists and industry professionals in the fields of offshore geotechnical engineering, centrifuge modelling, and renewable energies; iii) will monitor the progression of the research project; iv) will support the ER in overcoming the issues during the development of the project and suggest solutions.

Planned training activities for the researcher: the ER possesses skills in developing and implementing experimental programs in geotechnical centrifuges since the conception of the projects to the execution of the experiments, dissemination, communication and production of deliverables. Most of this expertise has been developed in projects associated with cyclic loading of subsoils characteristic of offshore environments^{42 43}. The ER is constantly seeking to integrate recent technology developments with centrifuge testing, for example, Digital Image Correlation (DIC) to measure deformations of the soil under dynamic loading⁴⁴ and currently studying the implementation of photogrammetry and 3D scanning methods to inspect soil/structure failure mechanisms⁴⁵. ShareWind will provide the ER significant experience in centrifuge testing and numerical modelling, hosted by a worldwide reference laboratory in centrifuge modelling and mentored by lead researchers in the area.

Scientific and technical skills: the training will reinforce the current ER scientific skills to address the objectives of this proposal and to advance in his career development plan. The ER will become proficient in definition of cyclic loads to be applied on shared anchors, numerical and analytical modelling of anchors subjected to complex loading (**WP1**) during the secondment at the NGI by regular meetings with the secondment supervisor and training by experienced researchers at the institute. At the Uni.Eiffel, the ER will be in charge of the preparation and scheduling of the centrifuge experiments (**WP2**) with the host lab team of technicians in activities as: development of experimental checklists, preparation of reconstituted clay, installation of sensors, actuators, configuration of data acquisition systems. This will lead to enhance teamwork skills, project monitoring, resources allocation and integration as collaborator in the host laboratory. The ER will acquire knowledge from Dr. Thorel in methodologies to install anchors in centrifuge models and implement them in ShareWind. At the Univ. of Southampton, under the training and mentoring of the secondment supervisors, the ER will bring to the host lab analysis skills in the advanced processing of numerical and experimental results towards the identification of design methodologies for shared anchors in clay (**WP3, WP4**). Formal training will be conducted by the ER in 3D photogrammetry at the Uni.Eiffel⁴⁶ and online courses in extended reality⁴⁷ as part of **WP3** consisting on implementing Digital Twins in the project.

Personal and transferable skills: during the fellowship, the ER will improve further his abilities for writing publications, reviewing articles and preparation of research proposals by participating in the workshops and courses offered by the Uni. Eiffel⁴⁸(ERC Training Pack) during the first semester of the fellowship. This set of skills will enhance the ER foundations for the preparation of future research proposals, for instance, the European Research Council (ERC) Starting grants. As the Open Science and entrepreneurship are a new topics to the ER, courses and workshops will be taken (i.e., Sorbonne University Open Science MOOC⁴⁹ and Uni.Eiffel CIPEN training⁵⁰). Those skills are fundamental for the implementation and update of the data management plan of ShareWind and to develop knowledge and awareness on entrepreneurship, data protection and intellectual property for future projects. The ER will extend his academic and industry network by participating as organizing committee member of the International Symposium on Frontiers in Offshore Geotechnics⁵¹ to be host in Nantes in 2025. The ER will contribute in mentoring activities at Uni. Eiffel by co-supervising at least two MSc students and delivering training in concepts of centrifuge modelling applied to offshore geotechnical engineering problems. As ShareWind will take place in France, the ER will enhance his skills in communication in French language as part of his integration in the host country by taking language courses offered by the HR division of Uni. Eiffel. **The proposed training plan will allow the ER to significantly deepen his expertise, in geotechnical design of offshore foundations, centrifuge and numerical**

³⁹ <https://asiriplus.fr/>

⁴⁰ <https://project-geolab.eu/universite-gustave-eiffel/>

⁴¹ Eolink – Cost effective renewable energy. <http://eolink.fr/en/>

⁴² Soriano, C., et al., “Simulation of a weak layered profile using geotechnical centrifuge,” Geotechnical Engineering in the XXI Century: Lessons learned and future challenges N.P. Lopez-Acosta et al. (Eds.). IOS Press

⁴³ Soriano, C., et al., 2022., “Centrifuge modelling of the seismic behavior of soft clay slopes”. ASCE Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering.

⁴⁴ Soriano et al., 2021, “ Seismic Centrifuge Modeling of a Gentle Slope of Layered Clay, Including a Weak Layer” Geotechnical Testing Journal. Vol 45(1)

⁴⁵ Personal website: <https://sites.google.com/unal.edu.co/cristiansoriano/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.ensg.eu/Formations-a-distance#cfc2>

⁴⁷ Virtual Reality Specialization – University of London – Coursera <<https://www.coursera.org/specializations/virtual-reality>>

⁴⁸ List of courses offered by the Uni. Eiffel.<[Brochure_FC_VF_WEB.pdf](#) (univ-gustave-eiffel.fr)>

⁴⁹ Sorbonne University, Open Science. <<https://www.fun-mooc.fr/en/courses/open-science/>>

⁵⁰ Universite Gustave Eiffel CIPEN training <<https://cipen.univ-gustave-eiffel.fr/>>

⁵¹ International Symposium on Frontiers in Offshore Geotechnics⁵¹

modelling applied to renewable energies, open science, and development of joint research projects. The skillset developed throughout ShareWind will represent a step forward in the ER career aimed at becoming an independent researcher and consulting engineer in the field of offshore geotechnical engineering applied to renewable energies solutions.

Two-way transfer of knowledge between the researcher and the host organization: in ShareWind, there will be a bi-directional exchange between the ER expertise in the preparation of centrifuge models involving clay and implementation of techniques of DIC image processing, photogrammetry and 3D scanning and the expertise and experience of Uni.Eiffel supervisor and technical staff in the development of experimental programs involving complex loading in offshore foundations. Both parts will benefit from this exchange as ShareWind will contribute to the Uni. Eiffel EMERGE⁵² group portfolio, a dissemination platform that gathers all the experience of the Uni.Eiffel in research and consultancy in coastal and offshore engineering. The workflow to be developed for the reconstruction of 3D models and DIC techniques applied to the centrifuge experiments in the frame of ShareWind can be extended for other test programs at the Uni. Eiffel geotechnical centrifuge. Advice and expertise will be provided by the ER for the acquisition of equipment as sensors, cameras and materials for the current and new experimental programs at the host lab. The transfer of knowledge to the host organization and secondment institutions will be in the form of workshops, demonstrations, research reports and training delivered by the ER to fellow researchers and postgraduate students interested in centrifuge modelling techniques, simulation of complex loading, DIC and 3D photogrammetry. The ER will bring to the host lab new research partnerships and knowledge: i) from the NGI, the latest techniques of geotechnical characterization of sites suitable for offshore wind solutions and optimization physical modelling strategies to link the centrifuge experiments with representative offshore environments; and ii) from the Univ of Southampton in 3D finite element modelling of offshore foundations and constitutive modelling, expertise areas in which the host lab is planning to develop new research lines.

1.4 Quality and appropriateness of the researcher's professional experience, competences and skills.

The ER has 3 years of professional experience as geotechnical engineer and 1.25 years of postdoctoral experience with a record of publications in topics associated with ground improvement, centrifuge modelling, soil dynamics, numerical modelling and offshore geotechnical engineering with emphasis in clayey soils (6 conference papers, 4 papers in high profile journals). This experience is backed by the ER doctoral dissertation with Prof. M. Almeida at the Federal Univ. of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ), and Prof. G. Madabhushi at the Univ. of Cambridge (1-year visitor PhD student) in which **the ER planned, performed and allocated resources to 7 centrifuge tests at the geotechnical centrifuge of the Univ. of Cambridge (Brazil-UK collaboration) and implemented a Digital Image Correlation workflow to track deformations of slopes under seismic loading**, expertise useful to **WP1** and **WP2**. Subsequent to obtaining the PhD in 2021, the ER worked as postdoc fellow at the UFRJ for 4 months, where he contributed in the **preparation of a research proposal accepted by Vale mining company to study static liquefaction of tailings and in the co-supervision of 2 M.Sc students, in projects related to the seismic response of offshore submarine slopes (currently in course)**. Experience applied in the preparation of ShareWind proposal to obtain MSCA funding and for the transfer of knowledge to Uni.Eiffel demonstrating skills of mentoring graduate students. Since October 2021, the ER participates as postdoc fellow at Uni.Eiffel in the project ASIRI+⁵³, funded by the French Research Agency (ANR). In this project, the ER works in the centrifuge modelling of soft clay ground profiles reinforced by piles subjected to seismic loading. This experience has been the opportunity to develop an independent profile as a researcher in centrifuge modelling and an insertion into Uni.Eiffel research environment. During the professional trajectory and MSc studies the ER developed skills in numerical modelling in PLAXIS of problems involving soft clays⁵⁴. Expertise required for the development of **WP3** and **WP4** that will be further reinforced during the secondment periods at the NGI and Southampton by receiving advise and training by expert researchers in the numerical modelling of anchors for floating wind turbines.

The ER has received awards and funding evidencing his academic excellence: dean's list at 4 periods during undergraduate studies in Colombia, MSc and PhD fellowships awarded in Brazil on the basis of his exceptional academic achievement (Nota 10 fellowships⁵⁵) and recipient of honorable mention (2nd place) of the Brazilian Society of Soil Mechanics for the best thesis in geotechnical engineering defended in Brazil in the period 2021-2022. Up to date, the ER has a record of service to the academic community as peer reviewer in five indexed research journals (12 reviews verified in Web of Science) and committee member of 3 MSc dissertations and 1 PhD qualifying exam.

2. Impact #@IMP-ACT-IA@#

2.1 Credibility of the measures to enhance the career perspectives and employability of the researcher and contribution to his/her skills development.

Impacts in the future career perspectives (WP6): The industry of floating offshore wind energy is expected to grow

⁵² EMERGE (Civil Engineering for Coastal and Offshore Structures) <https://emerge.univ-gustave-eiffel.fr/en/>

⁵³ ASIRI+ Amélioration & Renforcement des sols. <https://asiriplus.fr/les-pn-dans-le-retro-2021-une-annee-fructueuse-pour-les-actions-de-recherche-dasiri/>

⁵⁴ Hosseinpour., I, Soriano., C and Almeida, M.S.S "A comparative study for the performance of encased granular columns," Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering, 2019.

⁵⁵ Fundação de Apoio a Pesquisa do Estado do Rio de Janeiro scholarships. <https://www.faperj.br/?id=85.5.4>

and is a hot topic, hence, early contributions as the proposed in ShareWind will make the ER a reference in the area. Working at the host institutions, the ER will develop a research network with leading researchers and industry professionals in his field, both from France and abroad expanding his expertise and improving the quality and dissemination of his work. The job market in the offshore renewable energies industry is extremely competitive and successfully leading this project while holding the prestigious MSCA fellowship will promote the ER into the first ranks of researchers specializing in, and will allow him to apply for prestigious grants as ERC and positions as staff researcher in research/consulting institutes. Prior to the submission of ShareWind, the ER developed a career development plan (**WP6 deliverable**) and discussed it with Dr. Thorel to jointly devise a route in the next 3-4 years:

- **Short term plans:** One of the aims of the career development plan is establishing a research group with links between academic and industrial sectors. Upon the first year of completion of the MSCA fellowship, the ER will apply for a permanent position within Europe in a research/consulting institute (i.e., the NGI) or at a University (i.e., Uni. Eiffel). The ER will continue his academic production with at least two peer reviewed papers per year.

- **Long term plans:** the aim of the ER path is to become a senior researcher or senior consulting engineer aiming at leading a group of researchers or engineers in offshore geotechnical engineering projects. The ER will apply to the French accreditation to supervise research (HDR⁵⁶) as part of a plan to obtain an official recognition of his scientific level and to have a formal habilitation to supervise and evaluate PhD thesis in France. In terms of future research directions, this will most likely involve academy and industry efforts in developing geotechnical engineering solutions to the renewable energies industry considering the EU and worldwide targets to decarbonize the energy production. Therefore, ShareWind, under the MSCA fellowships program, is a step in this career development direction.

2.2 Suitability and quality of the measures to maximise expected outcomes and impacts, as set out in the dissemination and exploitation plan, including communication activities. #@COM-DIS-VIS-CDV@#

In the frame of the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDER) of **WP5** including communication activities, three target audiences and dissemination objectives have been identified: **TA1**) academic and research and development community, in particular in the areas of physical and numerical modelling of mooring systems for floating wind turbines; **TA2**) industrial sector: leading European companies (i.e., Total Energies, EDF), emerging SMEs, EU societies such as offshore wind energy, insurance companies, civil engineers and planners; **TA3**) general public with interest renewable energies, graduate students and Marie Curie fellowships candidates.

The measurable outcomes defined for the PDER of ShareWind concerning **TA1(academic)** and **TA2(industry)** are: at least **three conference papers** on international events, ECSMGE⁵⁷ (Aug. 2024), WindEurope (Apr. 2024)⁵⁸, Panamerican Conference on Soil Mechanics (Nov. 2024)⁵⁹; at least **two open access papers** in high-ranked scientific journals: International Journal of Physical Modelling in Geotechnics (IF 1.68), Geotechnique(IF 5.54), Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering (IF 2,70); **One database** of the project in an open access repository. To ensure the project reach a broad audience, Open Access will be assigned to all peer-reviewed publications. Open Access fees will be paid from the budget; **at least two** talks in the Scientific and Technical Days of the French Committee of Soil Mechanics as part of the communication activities of the project in the host country.

Concerning **TA3 (general)**: participation in at least **two exhibitions in science popularization events** as the EU researcher's night, Open Days at the Uni. Eiffel and "Science is Wonderful" and at least **one presentation of the project in the host countries of the secondment periods** (Norway and the UK) and in the country where the ER did graduate studies (Brazil) as the ER collaborates with his PhD thesis supervisor (co-supervision of MSc students);

(TA1-3): one website indexed in Uni. Eiffel EMERGE group devoted to the fellowship project including the details of the project and information about offshore floating wind turbines in the format of videos and animations and training materials (workshop files, tutorials). Blog entries will describe the experience as Marie Curie Fellow written in non-technical language and a version of the blog in a second language (Spanish, Portuguese or French). Support from communications office of Uni. Eiffel will be provided to obtain an institutional website (sharewind.univ-gustave-eiffel.fr), the website will be updated monthly by the ER; creation of **one LinkedIn** page and **one Twitter** account to share updates about the project and the offshore wind industry.

Uni. Eiffel, NGI and Univ. Of Southampton have agreed that the main intellectual property (IP) principles from Horizon Europe will apply to the background and foreground needed to carry out the project: a) **Partner background** remains in the ownership of the partner who provided it and the foreground will be owned by the partners who generate it. Access rights to background and foreground will be granted royalty-free for carrying out the project. b) Results arising from the project remain the property of the participant who has generated them. In case of joint ownership of results, generic provisions for use will be defined in a partnership agreement. Appropriate IP measures will be taken to protect any result arising from the project. Additional support could be provided by Uni.Eiffel to fostering the use of academic research results and technology transfer. ShareWind team will work

⁵⁶ Doctorates and HDR at UGE. <https://modele.univ-gustave-eiffel.fr/la-recherche/doctorats-et-hdr>

⁵⁷ European Conference on Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering. <https://www.ecsmge-2024.com/>

⁵⁸ Wind Europe annual event 2023. <https://windeurope.org/annual2023/>

⁵⁹ <https://panamgeo Chile2024.cl/>

closely with the Direction of Intellectual Property and Contracts, which is dedicated to this task and situated close to the lab.

2.3 The magnitude and importance of the project’s contribution to the expected scientific, societal and economic impacts.

Expected scientific impacts: with a baseline of no published research regarding multidirectional load on anchors installed in clay a condition that has to be addressed for future floating wind farms. The scientific outputs such as centrifuge model preparation techniques, numerical modelling workflows, publications, reports and data generated by the project can be utilized by the scientific community for future research. For example, the high-quality experimental data of the soil/anchor deformations and load capacity can be integrated in the calibration of numerical and constitutive models. The implementation of 3D scanning and photogrammetry to obtain digital reconstructions of the experiments will be reference in future physical modelling experimental programs.

Expected technological impacts: as no guidelines regarding the geotechnical design of shared anchors in clay are available, the outcomes of, ShareWind will provide information of the technical feasibility, of shared anchors as a solution to reduce costs of floating wind farms⁶ (around 16%). Design guidance and an experimental database for benchmarks will also be provided, as this information is useful to support the certification of the technology by bodies, e.g. the Det Norske Veritas (DNV). The project will provide information about the monotonic and multidirectional loading behavior of anchors with geometries and properties currently used in the offshore industry, outcomes relevant for anchor designers and suppliers. The project workflow will extend the possibility of testing different anchor types and technologies developed by industry designers involved in offshore wind farms.

Expected societal impacts: ShareWind is expected to contribute in the technology readiness of floating wind turbines, in the long term, the implementation of floating wind farms at an operational level will be dynamizing pole of the economy: development of local supply chains and workforce⁶⁰ (projections indicate over 20000 jobs in France in 2050). Recent EU investments⁶¹ (€210 million) co-financed by the European Investment Bank for the construction of floating wind farms in the French Mediterranean coast evidence the efforts of implementing this solution as part of the energy transition in France and ShareWind is aligned with those strategic investments.

#SCOM-DIS-VIS-CDV\$#

3. Quality and Efficiency of the Implementation #@WRK-PLA-WP@# #@CON-SOR-CS@# #@PRJ-MGT-PM@#

3.1 Quality and effectiveness of the work plan, assessment of risks and appropriateness of the effort assigned to work packages

The implementation of the project will follow the organization of the objectives and methodology presented in section 1, with a duration of 24 months (target starting month: June 2023). The plan is partitioned into six working packages (WPs) – 4 scientific **WP1** to **WP4** and 2 transversal (**WP5** and **WP6**) - as shown in ShareWind Gantt Chart with their interdependencies (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Gantt chart summarizing the work plan of ShareWind project

WP1: definition of cyclic (number of cycles) and monotonic loads, anchor geometries and seabed condition developed in the Months (M) M1-M4. **Milestones:** **MS1** -end of secondment at the NGI, definition of prototype conditions for the centrifuge tests. **Deliverables:** **D1.1 (M4)** report presenting the methodologies to define the monotonic and dynamic loads to be applied to the anchors, list of anchor geometries suitable for clay seabed and anchor installation considerations. **Dependence:** first working package that will provide the inputs of **WP2**.

WP2 subdivided in: **WP2.1** design of experimental set-up, **WP2.2** performance of centrifuge tests and

⁶⁰WindEurope <<https://windeurope.org/newsroom/news/france-commits-to-40-gw-offshore-wind-by-2050/>>

⁶¹European Commission, Press release June 28 2022 <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_22_4155>

WP3.3 determination of experimental soil/anchor failure envelopes it covers the Months M4 to M14. **Milestones:** **MS2** – end of the experimental campaign. **Deliverables:** **D2.1 (M14)** standardized data reports of the centrifuge tests accompanying the processed datasets uploaded in the project repository. **Dependence:** the parameters of geometry and soil types defined from **WP1**.

WP3: numerical modelling including the choice of parameters, constitutive models and Digital Twins, from Month M3 to M16; **Milestones:** **MS3** – calibration of the numerical models to move to parametric analyses. **Deliverables:** **D3.1(M16):** workflow report to implement the numerical simulations. **Dependence:** can start at month 3 of **WP1** with preliminary numerical simulations and refinements as **WP2** provides experimental results.

WP4: parametric analysis, theoretical framework, shared anchors design methodology it covers Months M16 to M21. **Milestones:** **M4** – culmination of the analyses, preparation of final deliverables. **Deliverables:** **D4.1(M21):** report summarizing the numerical analyses performed to develop the design charts and equations. **Dependence:** outcomes from the calibrated numerical models from **WP3**.

WP5: dissemination, communication and exploitation actions is a continuous WP that covers the 24 months of the project. **Milestones:** **MS5** – submission of the last project deliverable. **Deliverables:** **D5.1:** Data Management Plan (DMP), 1st version at month 6 (**M6**) of the project and two updates at months 12 (**M12**) and 24 (**M24**); **D5.2:** Scientific publications: at least two paper preprints submitted in journals (**M20, M22**) and three conference papers (**M11, M15, M18**); **Dependence:** advance of activities at the NGI, first dissemination action.

WP6: career development and training actions (at least 1 course or training each three months), it covers all the project duration M1-M24. **Milestones:** **M6** – new research and personal skills at the end of the project. **Deliverables:** **D6.1** career development plan report updated each 6 months. **Dependence:** the first training can take place since the start of the project, no enrollment deadlines in certified online MOOCS (i.e., edx or Coursera).

Allocation of time and resources: The research, training and networking resources will be dedicated to (i) purchase of 3D lidar scanner (600€), manufacture of anchors (200 €/anchor), purchase of clay reusable for the experiments (850 €); (ii) travel costs to attend conferences (travel subsistence, meeting fees, collaborative dinners with team members); (iii) fees of online courses to follow certified paths in Coursera, EDX and TuDelft platforms; and (iv) granting open-access to peer-reviewed papers. The numerical models, will be carried out in a conventional lab. laptop (CORE i7, 16GB ram). The ER will allocate 10% of time to training and mentoring activities. Weekly monitoring and resources allocation meetings will be organized with the project supervisor.

The risks of the project are defined in terms of risk level, which is a function of the risk probability and the severity on the impact of the project (Fig. 6).

		Risk (R)		
		Probability (L)		
Impact (I)	High	3	6	9
	Medium	2	4	6
	Low	1	2	3

Figure 6. Definition of risks

Description of risk probability, impact and level	WPs(s) involved	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Malfunction of actuators or sensors probability, M.; Impact, H; Level, 6	WP2	It was assigned a duration of 4 months to WP2.1 to test the equipment and perform at least a trial experiment in the centrifuge.
Excessive computation time probability, M.; Impact, M; Level, 4	WP3,WP4	Simplify the numerical models (less mesh elements) use a higher capacity computer (lab customized station 64GB Ram, Core i7 PRO).
COVID-19, or travel restrictions probability, M.; Impact, M; Level, 4	WP5,WP6	Participation on hybrid conferences, online meetings with host institutions supervisors (Microsoft Teams, Zoom or similar).
Loss of Data probability, L.; Impact, H; Level, 3	--ALL--	Project data will be stored simultaneously in hard drives, in the lab data server and extra copies stored in cloud data server (Google Drive).

3.2 Quality and capacity of the host institutions and participating organizations, including hosting arrangements

Uni. Eiffel has experience in management of EU funded projects including MSCA fellowships. This will benefit the ER. The project will benefit greatly from the methodological expertise developed at the host lab through its 37 years of existence. The ER will have the support of 5 staff technicians at the different stages of the preparation of the centrifuge experiments. The host lab has an excellent environment for the exchange of ideas with the experienced permanent researchers (five), doctoral students (three) and postdocs (two). Uni. Eiffel is supported by the Foreign Researchers in Nantes organization, member of Euraxess and the ER can benefit from their services: visas and residence permits, accommodation, health insurance, family issues, French courses and cultural activities. The ER will be seated in campus of Nantes (France) and will be provided with: i) an equipped office; ii) access to department facilities including libraries, experimental facilities and laboratory equipment (actuators, transducers, load cells, model containers, clay mixer, data logging systems); iii) access to facilities and tools for workshops (meeting rooms); iv) safety equipment for working in the laboratory area. The centrifuge at the Uni. Eiffel is the unique facility of its type in France and one of the largest centrifuges in the world. Uni. Eiffel geotechnical lab. participates in Horizon 2020 - GEOLAB (2021-2025), an international collaboration aimed at studying the interaction between critical infrastructure and the environment (the NGI is a partner). For the secondments, the NGI (307 permanent staff) and the Univ. of Southampton (6000 staff members) have experience in receiving researchers from all the world. The secondment institutions will provide a temporary office, support in administrative requirements and advise to arrange an accommodation in the host countries (Norway and the UK), no particular equipment will be used by the ER during the secondments for the development of his research. #§CON-SOR-CS§# #§PRJ-MGT-PM§#